

mental retardation, X-linked 58 or Tetraspanin-7 (TSPAN7 / MXS1 / TM4SF2) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : Tetraspanin-7 is a protein that in humans encoded by TSPAN7 gene. Tetraspanins (referred to as the transmembrane 4 superfamily (TM4SF) proteins) are a family of membrane proteins found in all multicellular eukaryotes. It has been implicated in urea cycle disorders, X-linked intellectual disability, multiple myeloma, HIV-1, osteoclasts, neurologic and psychiatric disorders, non-small-cell lung cancer, latent autoimmune diabetes in adults, Glucose-stimulated insulin secretion, bone resorption, osteosarcoma, glioma and obesity. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of TSPAN7, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the

*ML dicoveries of TSPAN7 synergy in Meningiomas

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combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: TSPAN7, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossil, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinghieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Tetraspanin-7 (TSPAN7)

Emi et al. [13] isolated a novel cDNA clone, called A15, via the differential screening of a cDNA library of an immature T cell line, HPB-ALL using radioactive cDNA probes from the mRNA of either HPB-ALL or peripheral blood lymphocytes. Further, they found that the A15 gene coded for a protein of 244 amino acids which contained 4 potential transmembrane domains and 4 possible N-linked glycosylation sites.

Herbst and Miller [14] found that X-linked forms of mental retardation (MR) affected approximately 1 in 600 males and were likely to be highly heterogeneous. They

could be categorized into syndromic (MRXS) and nonspecific (MRX) forms. Zemni et al. [15] showed that the gene TM4SF2 at Xp11.4 was inactivated by the X breakpoint of an X;2 balanced translocation in a patient with MR. Their further investigations led to identification of TM4SF2 mutations in 2 of 33 other MRX families. They also found that TM4SF2 was highly expressed in the central nervous system, including the cerebral cortex and hippocampus. It was observed that TM4SF2 encoded a member of the tetraspanin family of proteins, which were known to contribute in molecular complexes including β -1 integrins (Hemler [16]). They thus hypothesized that via this interaction, TM4SF2 might have a role in the control of neurite outgrowth.

1.3. Roles of TSPAN7 in different disease

Ornithine transcarbamylase (OTC) enzyme is involved in the urea cycle. The most common inherited disease of **urea cycle disorders** is the OTC deficiency, caused by impaired synthesis of OTC in the liver. Ono et al. [17] described the case of an OTC-deficient Japanese boy wherein an analysis based on SNPs revealed the absence of the entire OTC locus and nearby genes and identified a deletion on Xp11.4. This deleted region included genes encoding TSPAN7, MID1 interacting protein 1 (MID1IP1) and part of the retinitis pigmentosa GTPase regulator (RPGR) in addition to OTC. Further, they confirmed that the mother of the patient was a carrier of the mutation.

Mutations in TSPAN7 are implicated in some forms of **X-linked intellectual disability**. Bassani et al. [18] showed that TSPAN7 overexpression promoted the formation of filopodia and dendritic spines in cultured hippocampal neurons from embryonic rats, whereas its silencing reduced head size and stability of spines and AMPA receptor currents. Their findings indicated that, in hippocampal neurons, TSPAN7 regulated AMPA receptor trafficking by limiting PICK1 accessibility to AMPA receptors and suggested an additional mechanism for the functional maturation of glutamatergic synapses, whose impairment is implicated in intellectual disability.

Cheong et al. [19] investigated the expression of TSPAN7 in the haematological malignancy **multiple myeloma** (MM) and assessed the consequences of TSPAN7 expression in the adhesion, migration and growth of MM plasma cells (PC) in vitro and in bone marrow (BM) homing and tumour growth in vivo. They found that TSPAN7 highly expressed at the RNA and protein level in CD138⁺ MM PC from approximately 50% of MM patients.

Whereas human dendritic cells (DCs) are largely resistant to productive infection with **HIV-1**, they have a unique ability to take up the virus and transmit it efficiently to T lymphocytes through a process of trans-infection or trans-enhancement. To elucidate the molecular and cell biological mechanism for trans-enhancement, Ménager and Littman [20] performed an shRNA screening of genes involved in organelle and membrane trafficking in immature human monocyte-derived dendritic cells (MDDCs). They identified TSPAN7 and DNM2, which controlled actin nucleation and stabilization, as having important and distinct roles in limiting HIV-1 endocytosis and in maintaining virus particles on dendrites, which is required for efficient transfer to T lymphocytes.

Kwon et al. [21] investigated the role TSPAN7 isoform in the differentiation and function of **osteoclasts**. The observed up-regulation of TSPAN7 during osteoclastogenesis. Knock-down of TSPAN7 led to a striking cytoskeletal abnormality, i.e the for-

mation of the podosome belt structure was inhibited and the microtubular network were disrupted. Their results suggested that TSPAN7 played an important role in cytoskeletal organization required for the bone-resorbing function of osteoclasts by regulating signaling to SRC, PYK2, and microtubules.

The deregulation of dopaminergic signaling as a result of altered functionality of dopamine D2 receptor (DRD2) is implicated in multiple **neurologic and psychiatric disorders**. Lee et al. [22] tested the hypothesis that TSPAN7 might be a binding partner of DRD2 that was involved in the regulation of its functional activity. Their results showed that TSPAN7 was associated with DRD2 and reduced its surface expression by enhancing DRD2 internalization. Via immunocytochemical analysis, it was found that TSPAN7 resided in the plasma membrane and early and late endosomes promoted internalization of DRD2 and its localization to endosomal compartments of the endocytic pathway. Furthermore, they observed that TSPAN7 deficiency increased surface localization of DRD2, which was coincident with the decrease of its endocytosis, regardless of dopamine treatment. Finally, they observed that TSPAN7 negatively affected DRD2-mediated signaling. Their results disclosed a previously uncharacterized role of TSPAN7 in the regulation of the expression and functional activity of DRD2 by postendocytic trafficking.

125 lung cancer specimens and 60 metastatic tissues were obtained from patients diagnosed with **non-small-cell lung cancer** NSCLC, and Wang et al. [23] explored the effects and mechanisms of TSPAN7 on the progression of NSCLC cells. Their clinical data showed that among 125 patients with lung cancer, TSPAN7 was associated with lymph node status, differentiation, tumor size, and poor prognosis, while its knock-out inhibited cell proliferation and migration. They concluded that TSPAN7-mediated EMT was the key to NSCLC migration.

Shi et al. [24] investigated whether TSPAN7 autoantibodies (A) were valuable in predicting poor beta cell function in individuals with **latent autoimmune diabetes in adults** (LADA). They observed the prevalence of TSPAN7A in LADA (21.4% (37/173)), type 1 diabetes (26% (41/158)), type 2 diabetes (0.5% (1/204)) and healthy control participants (1.2% (2/170)). Further, they found that the measurement of TSPAN7A significantly increased the number of individuals with LADA found to be positive for multiple antibodies. They concluded that TSPAN7-A were valid islet autoantibodies for use in East Asian populations with autoimmune diabetes. Further, it could discriminate individuals with LADA who had lower beta cell function after disease progression.

Glucose-stimulated insulin secretion (GSIS) is regulated by calcium (Ca^{2+}) entry into pancreatic β -cells through voltage-dependent Ca^{2+} (Ca_V) channels. TSPAN proteins control Ca^{2+} handling, and TSPAN7 is the most abundant islet TSPAN and their immunostaining of mouse and human pancreatic slices showed that TSPAN7 was highly expressed in β - and α -cells. Dickerson et al. [25] showed that TSPAN7 knock-down (KD) increased glucose-stimulated Ca^{2+} influx into mouse and human β -cells. Further, it was observed that TSPAN7 KD enhanced L-type Ca_V currents in mouse and human β -cells. Conversely, heterologous expression of TSPAN7 with Ca_V 1.2 and Ca_V 1.3 L-type Ca_V channels decreased Ca_V currents and reduced Ca^{2+} influx through both channels. Finally, TSPAN7 KD in human β -cells increased basal (5.6 mM glucose) and stimulated (45 mM KCl + 14 mM glucose) insulin secretion. Their findings suggested that TSPAN7 modulation of β -cell L-type Ca_V channel was a key determinant

of β -cell glucose-stimulated Ca^{2+} entry and thus the set-point of GSIS.

Actin rings facilitate the attachment of osteoclasts to the bone matrix during **bone resorption**. TSPAN7 is known to play an important role in the reorganization of the cytoskeleton necessary for the bone-resorbing activity of osteoclasts. Kim et al. [26] investigated the roles of TSPAN7 in osteoclasts by deleting the TM4SF2 gene in mice, which encoded TSPAN7. Their global knockout model of TM4SF2 showed protective effects on pathological bone loss and demonstrated an association between TSPAN7 and the receptor activator of nuclear factor- $\kappa\text{B}/\alpha\text{v}\beta\text{3}$ integrin. Their findings suggested that TSPAN7 acted as a novel modulator regulating the bone-resorbing function of osteoclasts.

Shao et al. [27] demonstrated for the first time that TSPAN7 promoted **osteosarcoma** (OS) metastasis via interacting with β1 integrin and activating the FAK-Src-Ras-ERK1/2 pathway.

Glioma is the most common primary malignant tumor of the central nervous system in clinical practice. Chen et al. [28], by analyzing a large number of glioma cohorts, reported that TSPAN7 decreased in high-grade gliomas and this low expression was associated with poor prognosis in glioma patients. Further, by analyzing the relationship between TSPAN7 expression and immune cell infiltration in multiple datasets, they found that TSPAN7 was significantly -ively correlated with the immune infiltration of tumor-related macrophages, especially M2-type macrophages.

After previously identifying TSPAN7 as a candidate gene influencing body weight in an **obesity**-related gene screening study, Nemoto et al. [29] investigated the role of TSPAN7 from a metabolic perspective. They showed that TSPAN7 was involved in regulating lipid droplet formation and stabilization. Further, knockout of TSPAN7 in mice exhibited an increased proportion of small-sized adipocytes and a reduced visceral-to-subcutaneous fat ratio. Mechanistically, they observed that deficiency of TSPAN7 promoted subcutaneous fat expansion, thus alleviating metabolic stress on visceral fat, which was a major contributor to insulin resistance.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based

on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [30] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [31] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [31].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [32]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [33], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [30] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [30]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [34], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface us-

ing the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. TSPAN7 related synergies

Note - TSPAN7 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores

by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2nd order combinations of TSPAN7 were recorded.

3.1.1. TSPAN7 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with TSPAN7 showed high rankings - prominin 1 (PROM1), FRY microtubule binding protein (FRY), semaphorin 5B (SEMA5B), seizure related 6 homolog like (SEZ6L), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 1 inhibitor (PCSK1N), solute carrier family 17 member 7 (SLC17A7), olfactomedin 2 (OLFM2), EBF transcription factor 3 (EBF3), neurexin 2 (NRXN2), cut like homeobox 2 (CUX2), solute carrier family 29 member 1 (Augustine blood group) (SLC29A1), natriuretic peptide receptor 3 (NPR3), lysyl oxidase like 3 (LOXL3), proteoglycan 4 (PRG4), connective tissue growth factor (CTGF), collagen type X alpha 1 chain (COL10A1), RUNX family transcription factor 2 (RUNX2), HIVEP zinc finger 3 (HIVEP3), matrilin 3 (MATN3), sodium voltage-gated channel alpha subunit 7 (SCN7A), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 29 (TTC29), thrombospondin 1 (THBS1), dual oxidase maturation factor 1 (DUOXA1), dual oxidase 2 (DUOX2), secreted frizzled related protein 2 (SFRP2), spermatogenesis associated 9 (SPATA9), neurotrophic receptor tyrosine kinase 2 (NTRK2), phosphotyrosine interaction domain containing 1 (PID1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), coiled-coil-helix-coiled-coil-helix domain containing 6 (CHCHD6), collagen type XXVI alpha 1 chain (COL26A1), LDL receptor related protein 5 (LRP5), ELAV like RNA binding protein 4 (ELAVL4), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), frizzled related protein (FRZB), NK6 homeobox 1 (NKX6-1), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family B member 2 (APBB2), 15-hydroxyprostaglandin dehydrogenase (HPGD), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2 (DACT2), collagen type I alpha 2 chain (COL1A2), transmembrane protein 71 (TMEM71), sushi, von Willebrand factor type A, EGF and pentraxin domain containing 1 (SVEP1), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 12A (HSPA12A), microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4), lactate dehydrogenase D (LDHD), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily S member 1 (CYP2S1), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), nephronectin (NPNT), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), energy homeostasis associated (ENHO), armadillo repeat containing 4 (ARMC4), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), interleukin 17D (IL17D), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), NME/NM23 family member 9 (NME9), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), biglycan (BGN), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), colony stimulating factor 1

(CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1) and zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2^{nd} order combination of TSPAN7 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS TSPAN7									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T TSPAN7									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
PROM1 - TSPAN7	12	315	379	235	FRY - TSPAN7	36	218	222	361
SEMA5B - TSPAN7	204	137	254	362	SEZ6L - TSPAN7	98	242	304	318
PCSK1N - TSPAN7	207	102	330	322	SLC17A7 - TSPAN7	79	250	259	203
OLFM2 - TSPAN7	128	361	211	309	EBF3 - TSPAN7	331	62	267	369
NRXN2 - TSPAN7	15	279	230	317	CUX2 - TSPAN7	333	207	289	272
SLC29A1 - TSPAN7	298	153	345	347	NPR3 - TSPAN7	63	272	209	207
LOXL3 - TSPAN7	46	219	237	214	PRG4 - TSPAN7	189	241	279	212
CTGF - TSPAN7	305	114	224	242	COL10A1 - TSPAN7	188	278	281	220
RUNX2 - TSPAN7	281	221	236	339	HIVEP3 - TSPAN7	262	147	212	285
MATN3 - TSPAN7	132	319	206	222	SCN7A - TSPAN7	100	386	353	231
TTC29 - TSPAN7	86	236	375	260	THBS1 - TSPAN7	17	325	334	215
DUOXA1 - TSPAN7	50	246	240	289	DUOX2 - TSPAN7	278	248	243	344
SFRP2 - TSPAN7	139	260	344	204	SPATA9 - TSPAN7	152	214	269	288
NTRK2 - TSPAN7	9	261	365	279	PID1 - TSPAN7	21	252	226	239
EXT1 - TSPAN7	168	287	250	227	CHCHD6 - TSPAN7	85	268	376	237
COL26A1 - TSPAN7	254	201	106	250	LRP5 - TSPAN7	225	247	262	241
ELAVL4 - TSPAN7	173	311	253	226	MXRA8 - TSPAN7	233	307	339	56
NLRP3 - TSPAN7	136	295	355	254	FRZB - TSPAN7	236	158	261	353
NKX6-1 - TSPAN7	296	292	248	116	APBB2 - TSPAN7	182	333	338	60
HPGD - TSPAN7	215	289	215	351	DACT2 - TSPAN7	313	312	235	390
COL1A2 - TSPAN7	223	334	386	113	TMEM71 - TSPAN7	30	383	390	258
SVEP1 - TSPAN7	157	245	257	290	HSPA12A - TSPAN7	368	131	221	328
MFAP4 - TSPAN7	389	258	268	354	LDHD - TSPAN7	13	225	283	245
PRRT2 - TSPAN7	167	208	265	352	CYP2S1 - TSPAN7	381	364	374	252
NT5DC2 - TSPAN7	55	309	317	305	RAB31 - TSPAN7	265	318	297	234
NPNT - TSPAN7	231	302	325	61	VAMP5 - TSPAN7	226	262	290	202
ENHO - TSPAN7	386	184	276	340	ARMC4 - TSPAN7	319	294	316	17

Table 1: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between TSPAN7 VS Individual members.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS TSPAN7									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T TSPAN7									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
GPR183 - TSPAN7	58	392	340	205	ITGAM - TSPAN7	90	367	368	228
MAP6 - TSPAN7	273	164	285	262	MACROD2 - TSPAN7	156	380	318	216
STARD5 - TSPAN7	268	267	233	380	IL17D - TSPAN7	283	353	260	274
PEAK1 - TSPAN7	194	331	200	278	DNAH12 - TSPAN7	177	284	204	378
P2RY14 - TSPAN7	356	285	264	22	CABP4 - TSPAN7	119	343	354	293
SLCO3A1 - TSPAN7	311	316	287	8	BOK - TSPAN7	259	280	299	24
FZD8 - TSPAN7	40	370	323	251	MYOZ1 - TSPAN7	289	304	294	343
CSRNP3 - TSPAN7	116	384	358	244	NME9 - TSPAN7	195	288	251	319
EXT1 - TSPAN7	168	287	250	227	BGN - TSPAN7	301	249	322	48
PYCR1 - TSPAN7	326	291	333	73	FAM43B - TSPAN7	294	338	346	168
TMEM119 - TSPAN7	374	227	234	359	DUSP5P1 - TSPAN7	277	238	293	7
PRKD1 - TSPAN7	372	215	195	341	CSF1 - TSPAN7	24	366	370	263
FLRT2 - TSPAN7	94	313	296	329	SHC4 - TSPAN7	303	299	277	387
CYP4Z1 - TSPAN7	308	350	349	167	RTN4RL2 - TSPAN7	240	359	352	46
KBTBD12 - TSPAN7	245	259	356	44	LDLRAD2 - TSPAN7	286	204	228	57
ENTPD8 - TSPAN7	224	232	278	311	NUGGC - TSPAN7	299	293	301	391
DACT3 - TSPAN7	270	376	244	238	ADARB1 - TSPAN7	251	373	292	337
SPN - TSPAN7	161	340	332	266	CLEC9A - TSPAN7	285	200	146	392
DLGAP2 - TSPAN7	249	224	256	349	MMP17 - TSPAN7	343	217	120	200
DLL1 - TSPAN7	258	255	216	342	RYR3 - TSPAN7	83	244	205	313
RNU6-529P - TSPAN7	300	342	335	177	SYT15 - TSPAN7	379	360	291	39
FAM155A - TSPAN7	263	276	177	366	TMEM240 - TSPAN7	230	339	280	346
GPX3 - TSPAN7	323	213	123	334	RFPL1S - TSPAN7	349	298	307	277
LINC01907 - TSPAN7	237	265	347	256	ITGB2-AS1 - TSPAN7	184	282	227	386
LMCD1-AS1 - TSPAN7	365	275	314	21	ZNF883 - TSPAN7	250	329	288	106

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between TSPAN7 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t TSPAN7 with TSPAN7 – > PROM1 / FRY / SEMA5B / SEZ6L / PCSK1N / SLC17A7 / OLFM2 / EBF3 / NRXN2 / CUX2 / SLC29A1 / NPR3 / LOXL3 / PRG4 / CTGF / COL10A1 / RUNX2 / HIVEP3 / MATN3 / SCN7A / TTC29 / THBS1 / DUOXA1 / DUOX2 / SFRP2 / SPATA9 / NTRK2 / PID1 / EXT1 / CHCHD6 / COL26A1 / LRP5 / ELAVL4 / MXRA8 / NLRP3 / FRZB / NKX6-1 / APBB2 / HPGD / DACT2 / COL1A2 / TMEM71 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / MFAP4 / LDHD / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 / RAB31 / NPNT / VAMP5 / ENHO / ARMC4 / GPR183 / ITGAM / MAP6 / MACROD2 / STARD5 / IL17D / PEAK1 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / CABP4 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / CSRNP3 / NME9 / EXT1 / BGN / PYCR1 / FAM43B / TMEM119 / DUSP5P1 / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / RTN4RL2 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / NUGGC / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MMP17 / DLL1 / RYR3 / RNU6-529P / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / GPX3 / RFPL1S / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / ZNF883.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic TSPAN7 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of TSPAN7-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t TSPAN7	
PROM1 / FRY / SEMA5B / SEZ6L / PCSK1N ...	
SLC17A7 / OLFM2 / EBF3 / NRXN2 / CUX2 ...	
SLC29A1 / NPR3 / LOXL3 / PRG4 / CTGF ...	
COL10A1 / RUNX2 / HIVEP3 / MATN3 ...	
SCN7A / TTC29 / THBS1 / DUOXA1 / DUOX2 ...	
SFRP2 / SPATA9 / NTRK2 / PID1 / EXT1 ...	
CHCHD6 / COL26A1 / LRP5 / ELAVL4 / MXRA8 ...	
NLRP3 / FRZB / NKX6-1 / APBB2 / HPGD ...	
DACT2 / COL1A2 / TMEM71 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A ...	
MFAP4 / LDHD / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 ...	
RAB31 / NPNT / VAMP5 / ENHO / ARMC4 ...	
GPR183 / ITGAM / MAP6 / MACROD2 / STARD5 ...	
IL17D / PEAK1 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / CABP4 ...	
SLCO3A1 / BOK / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / CSRNP3 ...	
NME9 / EXT1 / BGN / PYCR1 / FAM43B ...	
TMEM119 / DUSP5P1 / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 ...	
SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / RTN4RL2 / KBTBD12 ...	
LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / NUGGC / DACT3 / ADARB1 ...	
SPN / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MMP17 / DLL1 ...	
RYR3 / RNU6-529P / SYT15 / FAM155A ...	
TMEM240 / GPX3 / RFPL1S / LINC01907 ...	
ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / ZNF883	TSPAN7

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TSPAN7 and Individual members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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